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A STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AND VALUE EDUCATION AMONG B.ED TRAINEES

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Abstract

The study analyses the B.Ed trainees' awareness & intentions of some common life skills and value education related actions. The study is based on primary data which is collected from 200 B.Ed trainees in and around Coimbatore district. The study explored the study on life skills and value education among B.Ed trainees towards teaching life skills as a way of developing practice of moral and positive social characteristic through the research. The findings reveal that there is no significant difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees. The Trainees shall be still encouraged to give more importance to life skills and value education. The same kind of study can be carried out by increasing the number of variables and factors to get the narrowed results. The same study may be extended to another geographical region. So as to generalize the findings of the present study or compare with other regions. In the similar manner further study can be conducted to analyze Life Skills and Value Education among all subject teachers at school level as well as college level.

Keywords: Life Skills; Value Education.

Cite This Article: Vijayarani.J, and Ms.Geetha.D. (2017). "A STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AND VALUE EDUCATION AMONG B.ED TRAINEES." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(8), 43-54. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.853182>.

1. Introduction

The main need of the study was to explore the Life skills and value education among B.Ed trainees towards teaching life skills education as a way of developing the practice of morality. It is practically impossible to teach without passing on some of the values that the teacher ascribes to. To even try to do so would be to suck the soul out of teaching. The simple act of teaching is about communicating certain values about commitment, preparation, discipline, timeliness, completeness, caring, attention curiosity, communication and many others. Value free teaching is not even possible. To achieve this, the aim of establishing the extent to which life skills education was being taught among B.Ed Trainees, how life skills education training had equipped teacher to teach it in schools and to identify challenges teachers were facing in implementing life skills education. In addition to recommend measures to be undertaken to

improve practice of morality in B.Ed colleges. The Life Skills Education will bring long term benefits to the society. These include educational, social, health, cultural and economic benefits.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

There are two main types of objectives undertaken by the investigator in this study work.

1.1.1. General Objectives

- 1) To Study on Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees in Coimbatore District.
- 2) To adopt questionnaire on Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees.

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

- 1) To find out the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees.
- 2) To find out the impact of personal variables like Gender, Medium of instruction, Location of the college, Nature of college, Type of family, Parents education, Parents occupation and Parents monthly income on Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees.

2. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study on life skills and value education among b.ed trainees. For this study a sample of 200 B.Ed trainees from seven B.Ed Colleges which are situated in and around Coimbatore district in Tamilnadu were selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique.

Table 1: Distribution of Samples based on Variables

S.NO	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Gender	Male	7	3.5%	200
		Female	193	96.5%	
2.	Medium of Instruction	Tamil	83	41.5%	200
		English	105	52.5%	
		Hindi	2	1%	
		Others	10	5%	
3.	Location of the College	Urban	79	39.5%	200
		Rural	121	60.5%	
4.	Nature of College	Boys	1	0.5%	200
		Girls	116	58%	
		Co-Education	83	41.5%	
5.	General Qualification	UG	99	49.5%	200
		PG	101	50.5%	
6.	Type of Family	Nuclear Family	174	87%	200
		Joint Family	26	13%	
7.	Educational Qualification of	Below 10	147	73.5%	200

	father	Diploma	9	4.5%	
		UG	34	17%	
		PG	9	4.5%	
		Professional	1	0.5%	
8.	Educational Qualification of mother	Below 10	151	75.5%	200
		Diploma	6	3%	
		UG	30	15%	
		PG	12	6%	
		Professional	1	0.5%	
9.	Occupation of Father	Daily Wagers	75	37.5%	200
		Farmer	28	14%	
		Govt.Job	13	6.5%	
		Private	27	13.5%	
		Business	56	28%	
		Others	1	0.5%	
10.	Occupation of Mother	Daily Wagers	53	26.5%	200
		Farmer	9	4.5%	
		Govt.Job	11	5.5%	
		Private	30	15%	
		Business	6	3%	
		Home Maker	91	45.5%	
11.	Monthly income of Father	Below Rs.5000	60	30%	200
		Rs.5000- Rs.15000	50	25%	
		Rs.15000- Rs.20000	57	28.5%	
		Above Rs.20000	33	16.5%	
12.	Monthly income of mother	Below Rs.5000	126	63%	200
		Rs.5000- Rs.15000	51	25.5%	
		Rs.15000- Rs.20000	12	6%	
		Above Rs.20000	11	5.5%	

Table 2: Scoring of each item

S.No	Dimension	Question No.	Scoring				
			Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	Effectiveness of a Life Skills Programme	1 to 20	5	4	3	2	1

Table 3: Ranks assigned for the scores

Effectiveness of a Life Skills Programme	
Scores	Rank
20 to 46	Low
47 to 72	moderate
73 to 100	High

HYPOTHESIS 1: There will be a significant mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on gender.

Table 4: Frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on gender.

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	0	0	5	71.43	2	28.57	7
Female	0	0	114	59.07	79	40.93	193

From the table 4 that amid the male students, 28.57% of them have high Level and 71.43% of them have moderate Level of Life Skills and Value Education. Similarly, amid the female students, 40.93% of them have high Level and 59.07% of them have moderate Level.

Table 5: 't' values between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to gender.

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Male	7	1.37	0.32	200	0.12	0.45	Not significant
Female	193	1.45	0.21				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.98)

From the table 5 the calculated value (0.12) is less than the table value of 't' (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to gender.

HYPOTHESIS 2: There will be a significant mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on location of the college.

Table 6: Frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on location of the college.

Locality	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Urban	0	0	62	78.48	17	21.52	79
Rural	0	0	57	47.11	64	52.89	121

From the table 6 that amid the urban area students, 21.52% of them have high Level and 78.48% of them have moderate Level of Life Skills and Value Education. Similarly, amid the rural area students, 52.89% of them have high Level and 47.11% of them have moderate Level.

Table 7: 't' values between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to location of the college.

Locality	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Urban	79	1.54	0.22	200	0.0004	0.499	Not significant
Rural	121	1.39	0.22				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.98)

From the table 7 the calculated value (0.0004) is less than the table value of 't' (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to location of the college.

HYPOTHESIS 3: There will be a significant mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on the educational qualification.

Table 8: Frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on the educational qualification.

General Qualification	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
UG	0	0	59	59.60	40	40.40	99
PG	0	0	60	59.41	41	40.59	101

From the table 8 that amid the UG qualified students, 40.40% of them have high Level and 59.60% of them have moderate Level of Life Skills and Value Education. Similarly, amid the PG qualified students, 40.59% of them have high Level and 59.41% of them have moderate Level.

Table 9: 't' values between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification.

Educational Qualification	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
UG	99	1.450	0.216	200	0.956	0.170	Not significant
PG	101	1.448	0.211				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.98)

From the table 9 the calculated value (0.956) is less than the table value of 't' (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification.

HYPOTHESIS 4: There will be a significant mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on the type of family.

Table 10: Frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed trainees based on the type of family.

Type of Family	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Nuclear Family	0	0	106	60.92	68	39.08	174
Joint Family	0	0	13	50	13	50	26

From the table 10 that amid the nuclear family students, 39.08% of them have high Level and 60.92% of them have moderate Level of Life Skills and Value Education. Similarly, amid the joint family students, 50% of them have high Level and 50% of them have moderate Level.

Table 11: 't' values between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to type of family.

Type of Family	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Nuclear	174	1.46	0.21	200	0.21	0.416	Not significant
Joint	26	1.40	0.23				

(At 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.98)

From the table 11 the calculated value (0.21) is less than the table value of 't' (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to type of family.

HYPOTHESIS 5: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to medium of instruction.

Table 12: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to medium of instruction.

Variable	Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Tamil	83	2.36	0.48
	English	105	2.45	0.50
	Hindi	2	2.00	0.00
	Others	10	2.30	0.48
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 12, it is concluded that the mean value of Tamil medium is 2.36 whereas the english medium is 2.45, the hindi medium is 2.00 and the others is 2.30. The result inferred that the mean value of English medium trainees is high compare to others.

Table 13: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to medium of instruction.

Medium of Instruction	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	46.63	3	15.54	1.08	0.43	Not Significant
Within group	2795.14	196	14.26			

From the table 13 calculated value of "F" (1.08) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.70, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to medium of instruction.

HYPOTHESIS 6: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to nature of college.

Table 14: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to nature of college

Variable	Nature of College	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Boys	1	2.00	0.00
	Girls	116	2.34	0.477
	Co-Educationa	83	2.49	0.503
	Total	200	2.40	0.492

From the table 14, it is concluded that the mean value of boys is 2.00 whereas the girls is 2.34 and the co-education is 2.49. The result inferred that the mean value of co-education trainees is high compare to others.

Table 15: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to nature of college.

Nature of College	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	71.95	2	35.98	2.56	0.26	Not Significant
Within group	2769.82	197	14.06			

From the table 15 the calculated value of "F" (2.56) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 3.09, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to nature of college.

HYPOTHESIS 7: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of father.

Table 16: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of father

Variable	Educational Qualification of father	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Below 10 th	147	2.41	0.49
	Diploma	9	2.77	0.44
	UG	34	2.26	0.44
	PG	9	2.33	0.50
	Professional	1	3.00	0.00
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 16, the mean value of Below 10th is 2.41 whereas the mean value of Diploma is 2.77, the mean value of UG is 2.26, the mean value of PG is 2.33 and the mean value of professional is 3. The result inferred that the mean value of professional is high compare to others according to the educational qualification of father.

Table 17: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of father.

Subject	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	75.42	4	18.85	1.33	0.39	Not Significant
Within group	2766.35	195	14.19			

From the table17, the calculated value of "F" (1.33) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of father.

HYPOTHESIS 8: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of mother.

Table 18: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of mother

Variable	Educational Qualification of Mother	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Below 10 th	151	2.37	0.48
	Diploma	6	2.50	0.54
	UG	30	2.40	0.49
	PG	12	2.66	0.49
	Professional	1	3.00	0
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 18, the mean value of Below 10th is 2.37 whereas the mean value of Diploma is 2.50, the mean value of UG is 2.40, the mean value of PG is 2.66 and the mean value of professional is 3. The result inferred that the mean value of professional is high compare to others according to the educational qualification of mother.

Table 19: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of mother.

Subject	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	56.27	4	14.07	0.99	0.48	Not Significant
Within group	2785.50	195	14.28			

From the table 19, the calculated value of "F" (0.99) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to educational qualification of mother.

HYPOTHESIS 9: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of father.

Table 20: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of father

Variable	Occupation of Father	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Daily Wagers	75	2.42	.49
	Farmer	28	2.46	.50
	Govt.Job	13	2.46	.51
	Private	27	2.40	.50
	Business	56	2.32	.47
	Others	1	3.00	.00
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 20, the mean value of daily wagers' is 2.42 whereas the mean value of Farmer is 2.46, the mean value of Govt.Job is 2.46, the mean value of Private is 2.40, the mean value of Business is 2.32 and the mean value of others is 3. The result inferred that the mean value of occupation of father coming under 'others' category is high compare to others.

Table 21: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of father

Subject	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	79.33	5	15.87	1.11	0.43	Not Significant
Within group	2762.44	194	14.24			

From the table 21, the calculated value of "F" (1.11) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.31, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of father.

HYPOTHESIS 10: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of mother.

Table 22: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of mother

Variable	Occupation of Mother	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Daily Wagers	53	2.37	0.48
	Farmer	9	2.44	0.52
	Govt.Job	11	2.18	0.40
	Private	30	2.43	0.50
	Business	6	2.50	0.54
	Home maker	91	2.42	0.49
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 22, the mean value of daily wagers' is 2.37 whereas the mean value of Farmer is 2.44, the mean value of Govt.Job is 2.18, the mean value of Private is 2.43, the mean value of Business is 2.50 and the mean value of Home maker is 2.42. The result inferred that the mean value of occupation of mother coming under 'Business' category is high compare to others.

Table 23: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of mother

Subject	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	39.61	3	19.63	1.39	0.38	Not Significant
Within group	2802.16	196	14.14			

From the table 23 the calculated value of "F" (1.39) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.31, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to occupation of mother.

HYPOTHESIS 11: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of father.

Table 24: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of father

Variable	Monthly income of father	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Below Rs.5000	60	2.43	0.49
	Rs.5000 – Rs.15000	50	2.32	0.47
	Rs.15000 – Rs.20000	57	2.42	0.49
	Above Rs.20000	33	2.45	0.50
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 24, the mean value of Below Rs.5000 is 2.43 whereas the mean value of 'Rs.5000-Rs.15000' is 2.32, the mean value of 'Rs.15000-Rs.20000' is 2.42 and the mean value of 'Above Rs.20000' is 2.45. The result inferred that the mean value of monthly income of father earning 'Above Rs.20000' is high compare to others.

Table 25: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of father

Subject	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	43.22	3	14.41	1.01	0.51	Not Significant
Within group	2798.55	196	14.28			

From the table 25, the calculated value of "F" (1.01) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.65, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of father.

HYPOTHESIS 12: There will be a significant mean score towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of mother

Table 26: Means score difference towards Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of mother

Variable	Monthly income of mother	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life Skills and Value Education	Below Rs.5000	126	2.40	0.49
	Rs.5000 – Rs.15000	51	2.39	0.49
	Rs.15000 – Rs.20000	12	2.50	0.52
	Above Rs.20000	11	2.36	0.50
	Total	200	2.40	0.49

From the table 26, the mean value of Below Rs.5000 is 2.40 whereas the mean value of 'Rs.5000-Rs.15000' is 2.39, the mean value of 'Rs.15000-Rs.20000' is 2.50 and the mean value of 'Above Rs.20000' is 2.36. The result inferred that the mean value of monthly income of mother earning 'between Rs.15000-Rs.20000' is high compare to others.

Table 27: 'F' ratio between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of mother

Subject	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Between group	39.61	3	13.20	0.92	0.57	Not Significant
Within group	2802.16	196	14.30			

From the table 27, the calculated value of "F" (0.92) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.65, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to monthly income of mother.

3. Results and Conclusion

- Female students have high level of Life Skills and Value Education than the male students.
- The rural area students have high level of Life Skills and Value Education than the urban area students.

- PG qualified students have slightly better Life Skills and Value Education than the UG qualified students.
- The joint family students have slightly better Life Skills and Value Education than the nuclear family students.
- There is no significant difference between Life Skills and Value Education among B.Ed Trainees with respect to gender, location of the school, educational qualification, type of family, medium of instruction, nature of college, educational qualification of father, educational qualification of mother, occupation of father, occupation of mother, monthly income of father and monthly income of mother.

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